

Bird Ecology in the Ruzizi Delta, Northern End of Lake Tanganyika in Burundi and in the Democratic Republic of Congo

Bashonga Bishobibiri Alexis¹, Eric Sande^{2*}, Gaspard Ntakimazi³ & Charles Kahindo⁴

¹Centre for Research in Hydrobiology (CRH) at Uvira, DRC

²Makerere University Kampala, Uganda*;

³University of Burundi Bujumbura

⁴State University of Bukavu (UOB), DR of Congo

Email : [*eric_sande@cns.mak.ac.ug](mailto:eric_sande@cns.mak.ac.ug)

ABSTRACT

Bird ecology in the Ruzizi Delta was investigated during the months of April, July and October 2019-2021. Three species of water birds were the most prominent, the Cattle Egret (Ardeidae), *Bubulcus ibis* (Linnaeus, 1758) «Héron garde boeufs», the Black Crake (Rallidae) *Amaurornis flavirostris* (Swainson, 1837) «Râle à bec jaune» and the African Jacana (Jacanidae) *Actophilornis africanus* (Gmelin, 1789) «Jacana à poitrine dorée». The objective pursued by the research is the sustainable conservation of birds by protecting their habitats, the wetlands of the Ruzizi Delta, particularly the unprotected Ruzizi Congolese Delta. The research documents 490 bird species including 99 (20%) in the unprotected Ruzizi Congolese Delta, 191 (39%) in the protected Rusizi Burundian Delta, and 200 species (41%) in both the Ruzizi Congolese Delta and Rusizi Burundian Delta. The research presents 60 newly reported species in the Ruzizi delta of which four are reported only in the unprotected Ruzizi Congolese Delta, 37 in the protected Rusizi Burundian Delta and 19 newly reported species both in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta and Rusizi Burundian Delta. The list of bird species now known from the Ruzizi Congolese Delta is extended by 21 species and goes from 252 to 273, while that of the Rusizi Burundian Delta is extended by 56 bird species and goes from 410 to 466. The 490 bird species are distributed into 18 orders and 84 families. 238 species meet six Ramsar criteria of seven for bird protection, of which only 29 are recorded in the unprotected Ruzizi Congolese Delta, 107 in the Rusizi protected Burundian Delta and 102 species are reported in both the Ruzizi Congolese Delta and Rusizi Burundian Delta. The thesis provides the needed information for the creation of a protected area in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta for sustainable conservation of birds and biodiversity in the Ruzizi delta both in Burundi, the DRC and the Northern End of Lake Tanganyika, already subscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List.

Key words: Bird ecology; water bird; Protection of wetlands; Density of bird species; Distribution of bird species.

INTRODUCTION

Bird ecology of birds tells us how Birds fit into the environment in which they live, and how they coexist with other organisms. There are two main aspects of bird ecology: feeding ecology and breeding ecology. We investigated some parameters of bird ecology focussing on three wetland bird species: Cattle Egret (Ardeidae), *Bubulcus ibis* (Linnaeus, 1758), «Héron garde boeufs»; Black Crake (Rallidae), *Amaurornis flavirostris* (Swainson, 1837), «Râle à bec jaune»; and African Jacana (Jacanidae) *Actophilornis africanus* (Gmelin, 1789), «Jacana à poitrine

dorée» in the low land of the Ruzizi Plain, main known as the Ruzizi Delta both in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) and in the Republic of Burundi.

How to Cite this Article:

Bashonga Bishobibiri Alexis, Eric Sande, Gaspard Ntakimazi, & Charles Kahindo. (2023). Bird Ecology in the Ruzizi Delta, Northern End of Lake Tanganyika in Burundi and in the Democratic Republic of Congo. *Biolife*, 11(1), 12-20.

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686228>

Received: 28 December 2022; Accepted: 18 February 2023;

Published online: 28 February 2023.

Sampling fieldwork were conducted two times per week, once in DRC and once in Burundi for eleven months from April 2019 to March 2020, except December 2019 as we were to Workshop in Benin and in Bukavu.

The main research question was how these three wetland bird species fit into their environment, the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) and the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) for their lasting conservation and management planning. We investigated the bird communities they live with, their feeding and breeding areas, stakeholder's opinions to protect their habitats along rivers, the Lake Tanganyika shore areas, in ponds and marshes surrounding ponds and rivers, as well as in steppe and shrub areas of the protected and unprotected areas in DRC and Burundi. The doctoral thesis on «Bird Ecology, Conservation and Management in the Ruzizi Delta of DRC and Burundi» is going along way to provide information needed for wetland habitats protection in DRC and enforcement bird conservation management both in DRC and in Burundi (Butchart, Stattersfield, & Collar, 2006).

This study is unique for Bird Ecology, Conservation and Management both in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) in DRC and in the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) in Burundi. It will update the list of birds both in the RCD and in the RBD. It will contribute to the expansion of protected areas in the DRC and to strengthening the management of protected areas in Burundi with a view to combating climate change, epidemics and disasters and preventing the extinction of certain species of birds

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Bird species communities include orders, families, resident, migrant bird species, species that fulfil the Ramsar criteria, and bird species with IUCN status. All of them are important bird species for conservation in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) and the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD)

Bird communities

Bird species communities include orders, families, resident, migrant bird species, species that fulfil the Ramsar criteria, and bird species with IUCN status. All of them are important bird species for conservation in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) and the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD)

Bird species number per Family and per order from the Ruzizi Delta

Table 1 presents the number of species (sp) and the number of families per order represented in the Ruzizi Delta. Orders represented are: **Podicipediformes**, one family Podicipedidae (3 sp); **Pelecaniformes**, three families: Pelecanidae (2 sp), Phalacrocoracidae (2 sp),

Anhingidae (2 sp); **Ciconiiformes**, four families: Ardeidae (16 sp), Scopidae (1 sp), Ciconidae (7 sp), and Threskiornithidae (4 sp); **Phoenicopteriformes**, one family Phoenicopteridae (5 species); **Anseriformes**, one family Anatidae (17 sp); **Falconiformes**, two families: Accipitridae (26 sp) and Falconidae (11 sp); **Galliformes**, two families: Numididae (1 sp) and Phasianidae (8 sp); **Gruiformes**, four families: Sarothruridae (3 sp), Rallidae (11 sp), Gruidae (3 sp) and Otididae (1 sp);

Table 1 Bird species numbers and family numbers per order from the Ruzizi Delta

Nb	Orders	FNb	SNb
1	Podicipediformes	1	3
2	Pelecaniformes	3	6
3	Ciconiiformes	4	28
4	Phoenicopteriformes	1	5
5	Anseriformes	1	17
6	Falconiformes	2	37
7	Galliformes	2	9
8	Gruiformes	4	18
9	Charadriiformes	12	67
10	Columbiformes	1	12
11	Psittaciformes	1	1
12	Cuculiformes	2	15
13	Strigiformes	1	6
14	Caprimulgiformes	1	4
15	Apodiformes	3	11
16	Coraciiformes	6	27
17	Paciformes	4	9
18	Passeriformes	35	215
	Total	84	490

Legend: Nb, Ordinal number; FNb, Family Number; SNb, Species Number

Charadriiformes, 12 families: Jacanidae (2 sp), Recurvirostridae (2 sp), Dromatidae (1 sp), Rostratulidae (1 sp), Burhinidae (2 sp), Glareolidae (5 sp), Charadriidae (19 sp), Scolopacidae (21 sp), Stercorariidae (2 sp), Laridae (4 sp), Sternidae (7 sp), and Rynchopidae (1 sp); **Columbiformes**, one family Columbidae (12 sp); **Psittaciformes**, one family Psittacidae (1 sp); **Cuculiformes**, two families: Musophagidae (2 sp), and Cuculidae (13 sp); **Strigiformes**, one family Strigidae (6 sp); **Caprimulgiformes**, one family (4 sp); **Apodiformes**, three families: Apodidae (7 sp), Coliidae (3 sp) and Trogonidae (1 sp); **Coraciiformes**, 6 families: Alcedinidae (9 sp), Meropidae (9 species), Coraciidae (3 sp), Phoeniculidae (2 sp), Upupidae (2 sp), and Lybiidae (2 sp); **Paciformes**, four families: Indicatoridae (4 sp), Picidae (2 sp); Eurylaimidae (1 sp), and Pittidae (1 species); and finally **Passeriformes**, 35 families: Alaudidae (4 sp), Hirundinidae (11 sp), Motacillidae (8 sp), Campephagidae (2 sp), Pycnonotidae (6 sp), Turdidae (12 sp), Acrocephalidae (8 sp), Locustellidae (2 sp), Sylviidae (3 sp), Scotocercidae (1 sp), Phylloscopidae (3 sp), Macrosphenidae (1 sp), Hyliotidae (1 sp), Cisticolidae (23 sp), Muscapidae (13 sp), Platysteiridae (1 sp), Monarchidae (3 sp), Pellorneidae (2 sp), Leiothrichidae (4

sp), Paridae (1 sp), Timaliidae (2 sp), Zosteropidae (1 sp), Nectarinidae (14 sp), Oriolidae (3 sp), Laniidae (7 sp), Malaconotidae (7 sp), Vangidae (1 sp), Dicruridae (1 sp), Corvidae (2 species), Sturnidae (9 species), Passeridae (2 sp), Ploceidae (28 sp), Estrildidae (19 sp), Viduidae (2 sp), and finally the Family of Fringilidae (8 sp). The 18 orders, 84 families and the number of 490 bird species from the Ruzizi Delta are presented by Table 1. The difference between the bird species numbers and the numbers of families per orders is significant (T^1 cal= 5,891; DF= 34; $p < 0.001$).

Bird taxonomic divisions from the Ruzizi Delta

Figure 1 presents taxonomic divisions of the bird species recorded in the Ruzizi Delta 2019-2020 including: 18 orders, 84 families and 490 species. There is a highly significant difference between the bird taxonomic divisions in the Ruzizi Delta, ($\chi^2 = 488,926$; DF=2; $p < 0.001$).

Figure-1. Taxonomic Divisions of Bird Species from Ruzizi Delta

We assume that the minimum respect of Congolese regulations for environment and biodiversity conservation (Chiambeng, Aziza, Mafuta, & Kasongo, La répression des crimes fauniques en RDC: comment améliorer les poursuites judiciaires? Rapport decembre 2018, 2018); (RDC, 2016) and (RDC C. P., 2003) may lead to the full protection of the banks of the rivers, natural ponds and the Lake Tanganyika shore areas at Uvira. Following are bird species fluctuation and bird densities per sampling area and per sampled sites in the Ruzizi Delta both in the DRC and the Republic of Burundi.

Bird Species occurrence in the Ruzizi Delta

We recorded 490 bird species of which 99 (20%) in the unprotected Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD), 191 (39%) in the protected and Ramsar site of Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD), and 200 (41%) species both in the RCD and in the

RBD (Figure 2). There is a significant difference of bird occurrence between the unprotected RCD and the protected RBD ($\chi^2 = 38.257$; DF= 2; $p < 0.001$).

Figure 2 Bird Species Occurrence in the Ruzizi Delta 2019-2021

Resident bird species occurrence in the Ruzizi Delta

Figure 3 presents occurrence of resident bird species in the studied areas of the Ruzizi Delta. Of 490 species, 359 (73%) are resident bird species. Of 359 bird species, 74 (21%) were recorded in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD), 148 (41%) were recorded in the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) and 137 (38%) were both recorded in the RCD and the RBD. The difference between resident bird species occurrence among sampled habitat areas of Ruzizi Delta is significant ($\chi^2 = 48, 31$; DF=2; $p < 0.001$).

Figure 3 Resident bird species occurrence in the Ruzizi Delta

Migrant bird species occurrence in the Ruzizi Delta

Figure 4 presents occurrence of migrant bird species in the Ruzizi Delta. Of 490 bird species recorded, 131 are migrant bird species. Of migrant species, 24 (18%) were

¹ T, Student t-test

recorded in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD), 44 (34%) in the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) and 63 (48%) migrant bird species were recorded both in the RCD and the RBD. The difference of occurrence of migrant bird species between sampling areas is significant ($\chi^2 = 17.42$; $DF=2$; $p < 0.001$).

Figure 4 Migrant bird species fluctuation in the Ruzizi Delta 2019-2021

The Ramsar Criteria fulfilled by the Ruzizi Delta

Fluctuation of the bird species that fulfil the Ramsar Criteria per sampling areas

Of 490 bird species recorded from the Ruzizi Delta, 238 fulfil six of seven Ramsar Criteria of bird conservation. Of them, 29 (12%) were recorded in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD), 107 (45%) in the Rusizi Burundian Delta, and 102 (43%) bird species were recorded both in the RCD and the RBD (Figure 5 and Figure 6). The Ramsar bird species occurrence between the sampled areas is highly significant in the Ruzizi Delta ($\chi^2 = 48,059$; $DF=2$; $p < 0.001$).

Figure 5 Bird species that fulfil the Ramsar Criteria fluctuation in the Ruzizi Delta

Legend: RCD, Ruzizi Congolese Delta; RBD, Rusizi Burundian Delta

Figure 6 The Ramsar Criteria fulfilled by the Ruzizi Delta in DRC and Burundi

Figure 7 presents bird species density per sampling areas, RCD (Ruzizi Congolese Delta) area and RBD (Rusizi Burundian Delta) area and per sampling sites. In RCD area, the bird species densities were: 75 bird species/ km² in the site of Kyamvubu (Kya); 165 in the site of Kavimvira Border Ponds (KBOP); 91 species in the site of Kahorohoro Village (Kah); and 64 bird species /km² in the site of Vugizo. The bird species density of the whole sampling RCD area was 86 bird species/ km².

Figure 7 Bird Species Density per sampling area and sampling site

In the area of RBD (Rusizi Burundian) area, the bird species densities were: 209/ km² in the site of GRRM (Great Rusizi River Mouth); 79 in the site of SSA (Steppe and Shrub Areas); and 135 bird species in the site of MuP (Mukartutsi Ponds. The bird density of the whole sampling area of RBD was 118 bird species/ km². The bird species densities of the protected Rusizi Burundian Delta were not significantly higher compared to the bird densities of the unprotected Ruzizi Congolese Delta ($\chi^2 = 0.112$; $DF= 6$; $p > 0.001$).

New bird species records from the Ruzizi Delta

Figure 8 presents the new bird species numbers recorded from the Ruzizi Delta. These are 60 new bird species records of which four from the Ruzizi Congolese Delta

(RCD), 37 from the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) and 19 new bird species records from both the RCD and the RBD. The difference of the distribution of the new bird species recorded between studied areas is highly significant ($\chi^2=27.3$; DF= 2; $p<0.001$).

Figure 8 New bird species records from the Ruzizi Delta

Three Wetland Bird Species densities in the Ruzizi Delta

Three wetland bird species were more intensively investigated by their individual counting and some ecological elements recording. These are: **Cattle Egret** (Ardeidae), «Héron garde boeuf» *Bubulcus ibis* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Black Crake** (Rallidae), «Râle à bec jaune», *Amaurornis flavirostris* (Swainson, 1837); and **African Jacana** (Jacanidae), «Jacana à poitrine dorée», *Actophilornis africanus* (Gmelin, 1789).

Figure 9 Wetland bird densities (Birds/ km²) in the Ruzizi Delta

Figure 9 presents the wetland bird densities per sampling areas (RCD and RBD) and per sampling sites for the above three species. The densities per sampling sites in RCD (Ruzizi Congolese Delta) area were: In DRC, 2 wetland birds /km² in the Kyamvubu site (Kya), in Kahorohoro Village site (Kah), and in the site of Vugizo (Vug); and

7 wetland birds/ km² in the site of Kavimvira Border Office Ponds (KBOP). In the whole area of Ruzizi Congolese Delta, the density was 1 wetland bird/ km². In Burundi, the densities were: 11 wetland birds/ km² in the site of Great Rusizi River Mouth (GRRM); 7 wetland birds/ km² in the site of Steppe and Shrub Areas (SSA); and finally 19 wetland birds/ km² in the site of Mukartutsi Ponds (MuP). The wetland bird species showed four records/ km² in the whole sampled area of Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD). The wetland bird densities were significantly higher in the protected wetland areas of the Rusizi Burundian Delta compared to the unprotected wetland areas of the Ruzizi Congolese Delta ($\chi^2_6= 31.500$; DF=6; $p<0.001$).

Wetland birds fluctuations per sampling periods

Figure 10 presents fluctuations of wetland birds per sampling periods in the Ruzizi Delta in 2019-2020. In the RCD (Ruzizi Congolese Delta), wetland bird fluctuations peaked in May with an average of seven recorded individuals and the minimum occurred in July, the least rainy month of the year with an average of three birds. In the RBD (Rusizi Burundian Delta), wetland bird fluctuations peaked as well in May with an average of 24 birds and the minimum occurred in July with an average of eight wetland birds. Yet, there is no significant difference of wetland bird fluctuations between the Ruzizi Congolese Delta and the Rusizi Burundian Delta due to similar habitats loss ($T^7_{cal}= 1.983$; DF= 20; $p>0.001$).

Figure 19. Wetland birds species fluctuations in the Ruzizi Delta

Constraints and limitations of the study

Constraints of the study

The constraints to bird ecology studies in the Ruzizi delta are linked to the difficulties of the Congolese and Burundian governments to finance fundamental research in order to bring out trends according to national research plans. National research plans sometimes do not exist or

⁶ χ^2 , Chi squared test

are dependent on electoral trends. A prime minister or a minister during an election period has a research plan drawn up in order to stay in power and sometimes he does not have the means to have it carried out. In the event of a change of government, previous plans are abandoned to develop so-called more innovative ones without budgetary or financial means to implement them.

This is why the few studies carried out are sometimes supported by external partners who at times impose their tendencies as a line of research to follow and after their funding, data collection stops. The Ruzizi Congolese Delta, for example, has not been the subject of any ornithological research supported by the DRC. The same is true for the entire Ruzizi Congolese Plain where only the Belgian Technical Cooperation had funded my research for my master's dissertation at Makerere University Kampala Uganda in 2010-2011.

The most apparent case is the Lake Tanganyika Congolese shoreline, about 677 km in length, where no recent ornithological study has been conducted. Species to be listed there for the first time and even new species are probably still ignored.

5.2 Limitations of the study

Limitations to bird ecology, conservation and management in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta are mainly due to the poor land distribution policy and non-compliance with laws on wetlands and biodiversity. These are given from the following extract of law no 011/2002 (Kabila, 2003).

CONCLUSION

In this chapter on bird ecology, we have reviewed the communities of birds that compete for natural resources, particularly plants as resting and breeding grounds in the Ruzizi Delta, namely 490 bird species divided into 84 families and in 18 orders. 56 new bird species records are made in the Rusizi Burundian Delta, shifting the bird species known there from 410 to 466. Similarly 23 new bird species records are made in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta, shifting the bird species now known there from 252 (Bashonga B. , 2013) to 275. Bird frequencies and densities are significantly higher in the protected areas of the Rusizi Burundian Delta compared with the unprotected areas of the Ruzizi Congolese Delta.

Birds in wetlands behave differently; The Cattle Egret adapts to anthropogenic variations in its environment, but the Black Crake cannot tolerate the destruction of marshes just as the African Jacana does not tolerate pond vegetation massive removal for fishing. Moreover, the African Jacana was not found in fast-moving water areas without vegetation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the DRC as in Burundi, we recommend compliance with regulatory texts on environmental protection with regard to the protection of wetlands, which are the bastions of biodiversity necessary for the well-being of current and future human communities; For the DRC, we recommend decision makers to create a protected area in the RCD wetlands which matches with the Ramsar Criteria for bird conservation and therefore a potential Ramsar site; For the Congolese Institute for Nature Conservation (ICCN), we recommend the submission of the RCD to the Ramsar Secretariat for designation as a Ramsar Site, as soon as it will be accepted as a protected area; For the provincial government of South Kivu, to take a decision agreement for a Community protected wetland of the RCD; For Mayor and territorial authorities, to sensitise people to wetlands protection referring to the Ramsar Convention ratified by the Congolese government and environmental regulations.

Acknowledgements

I am grateful to: the Doctoral School of University of Burundi for facilitating this research by issuing research papers; The Centre for Research in Natural Sciences and the Environment (CRSNE) and the Biodiversity, Ecology and Environment Laboratory (LBEE) of the University of Burundi; the Centre for Research in Hydrobiology (CRH) at Uvira, DRC for research equipment, research assistant personal, laboratory and library.

I acknowledge Louette Michel of the RMCA (Royal Museum of Central Africa) and John Bates of the FMNH (Field Museum of Natural History) to have trained me in bird identification, systematic and conservation techniques.

The staffs of the CRH-Uvira gave freely of their time and hospitality and are thanked with gratitude, particularly Prof. Nshombo Muderhwa for bird conservation documents.

Conflicts of Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- [1] Arendt, W. J. (1988). Range expansion of the Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) in the Greater Caribbean Basin. *Colonial Waterbirds* 11: 252–262, 10 pages.
- [2] Ashoor, A. (2010). Breeding Biology and Success of the Little Egret *Egretta garzetta* in Karfestan Abbandan, Roudsar, Gilan Province, Northern Iran. *Podoces*, 5(1): 29–34, 6 pages.

- [3] Bachir, A. S., Barbraud, C., RCéréghino, & Santoul, F. (2012). Cattle Egrets *Ardea ibis* use human made habitat in a newly colonised area in North-Algeria. *Ostrich* 83: 51–53, 3 pages.
- [4] Bachir, A. S., Ferrah, F., Barbraud, C., Céréghino, R., & Santoul, F. (2011). The recent expansion of an avian invasive species (the Cattle Egret) in Algeria. *Journal of Arid Environments* 75: 1232–1236, 4 pages.
- [5] Bank, W. (2018). *Lake Tanganyika Environmental Management Project (P165749), Project Information Document/ Integrated Safeguards Data Sheet (PID/ISDS)*. Washington DC, USA: Public Disclosure Authorized, 21 pages. <http://www.worldbank.org/projects/02/11/2021>.
- [6] Bashonga, B. (2013). *The Importance of Ruzizi Congolese Plain, South Kivu, DRC for the Conservation of Birds*. A dissertation submitted to the DRGT in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a degree of Master of Science in ENR of MUK, Uganda. Kampala: Makerere University, Kampala Uganda, 112 pages.
- [7] Bashonga, B. A. (2019). Public Awareness on the Reaction of Threats to Crocodiles and Hippopotami in the Ruzizi Plain and the Lake Shore in Uvira DRC, Northern End of Lake Tanganyika. *CEBioS, Buxelles*, 4 pages. <http://cebios.naturalsciences.be> 07/10/2021.
- [8] Bezuidenhout, J. D., & Stutterheim, C. J. (1980). A critical evaluation of the role played by the Red-billed Oxpecker *Buphagus erythrorhynchus* in the biological control of ticks. *Onderstepoort Journal of Veterinarian Research* 47: 51–75, 24 pages.
- [9] Bosque, C. (2009). Opportunistic blood-drinking by Black Crake *Amaurornis flavirostris*. *Ostrich: Journal of African Ornithology*, 80:1, 65–65, 1 page. DOI: 10.2989/OSTRICH.2009.80.1.11.769, 2.
- [10] Browser, J. E., Zar, J. H., & End, C. N. (1997). *Field and Laboratory Methods for General Ecology*. Boston & New York: WCB McGraw-Hill, 273 pages.
- [11] Butchart, S., Stattersfield, A., & Collar, N. (2006). How many bird extinctions have we prevented? *Oryx*, Vol. 40, no 3, 266–279, 13 pages.
- [12] Cabinet, P., & DRC. (2011). *Law n° 11/009 of July 9, 2011 on fundamental principles relating to the protection of the environment*. Kinshasa, DRC: Official Journal special issue July 16, 2011, 32 pages.
- [13] Cabinet, P., & DRC. (2014). Law No. 14/003 of February 11, 2014 relating to the conservation of nature. *State Journal of the DRC*, 17 pages.
- [14] Cardinal, B. J., Duffy, E., Gonzale, A., Hooper, D. U., Perrin, C., Venail, P., et al. (2012). Biodiversity loss and its impact on humanity. *Nature Volume 486 Number 7401* 59–67, 8 pages.
- [15] Chapman, A. D. (2005). *Numbers of Species Living in Australia and in the World. Report for the Department of the Environment and Heritage Canberra, Australia*. Canberra, Australia: Australian Biodiversity Information Services Toowoomba, Australia, 84 pages.
- [16] Chapman, A. D. (2009). *Numbers of Living Species in Australia and the World*. Canberra: Australian Biological Resources Study: 1–84 pages. ISBN 978-0-642-56861-8.
- [17] Chiambeng, P. N., Aziza, N. S., Mafuta, C. M., & Kasongo, E. D. (2018). *La répression des crimes fauniques en RDC: comment améliorer les poursuites judiciaires? Rapport décembre 2018*. Kinshasa: Traffic, 44 pages.
- [18] Crick, H. Q., Dudley, C., Glue, D. E., & Thomson, D. (1997). UK birds are laying eggs earlier. *Nature* 388, 526–526, 1 page.
- [19] Deanna, W. M., Brunner, J., Nige, I. S., Karr, C. J., & Nielsen, D. (1998). *Forests and the Democratic Republic of Congo Opportunity in a Time Crisis: A Contribution to the Forest Frontiers Initiative*. New York: World Resources Institute, 30 pages.
- [20] Deanna, W. M., Jake, B., Nigel, S., Catherine, K. J., & Daniel, N. (1998). *Forests and the Democratic Republic of Congo Opportunity in a Time Crisis: A Contribution to the Forest Frontiers Initiative*. New York: World Resources Institute, 30 pages.
- [21] Demey, R., & Louette, M. (2001). Democratic Republic of Congo. In L. D. Fishpool, & M. I. Evans, *Important Bird Areas in Africa and Associated islands: Priority Sites for Conservation*. Newbury and Cambridge (UK): Pisces Publications and Bird Life International (Bird Life Conservation Series No 11): 198–218, 20 pages.
- [22] Dowset, & Dowset-Lemaire. (1993). *A contribution to the Distribution and Taxonomy of Afrotropical and Malagasy birds Tauraco Research Report*. Liège, Belgium.: Tauraco Press, Jupille No. 5: 195–204, 9 pages.
- [23] Eagle, P., F.McCool, S., & Haynes, C. D. (2002). *World Commission on Protected Areas (WCPA) Sustainable Tourism in Protected Areas Guidelines for Planning and Management*. Gland Switzerland: The World Conservation Union, 191 pages.
- [24] Erwin, R. M., & Custer, T. W. (2000). Herons as indicators. Dans K. J. (eds), *Heron Conservation*. London, UK: Academic Press: 311–330, 19 pages.
- [25] FAO, & UKAID. (2015). *The legal framework for forest conversion in the Republic of Congo*. London, Brussels & Warsaw (Wales): ClientEarth, 39 pages. www.clientearth.org 01/11/2021.
- [26] Fielder, W. (2016). *Bird Ecology*. Radolfzell, Germany: Max Planck Institute for Ornithology, 30 pages.
- [27] Fishpool, L., & Evans, M. (2001). *Important Bird Areas in Africa and Associated Islands: priority sites for conservation*. Newbury and Cambridge, UK: Pisces Publications and BirdLife International (BirdLife Conservation Series No. 11), 1144 pages. www.birdlife.net 12/07/2022
- [28] Gaugris, Y. (1979). *Les oiseaux aquatiques de la plaine de la basse Rusizi (Burundi) (1973–1978)*. Paris-France:

- L'Oiseau et la Revue française d'ornithologie, volume 49 n° 21:33-153, 120 pages. <https://eurekamag.com/research/021/279/021279617.php> 18/06/2022.
- [29] Gaugris, Y., & Weghe, J. P. (1993). L'importance du delta de la Rusizi (Burundi) pour les migrateurs paléarctiques. Dans MRAC, *Proceedings of the Eighth Pan-African Ornithological Congress Birds and the African Environment*. Belgium: Annales zoologiques Vol.268: 546-552, 6 pages.
- [30] Guggisberg, C. (1986). *Birds of East Africa. Supra Safari Guide No 6 Volume II*. Nairobi Kenya: Mount Kenya Sundries, 196 pages.
- [31] Guggisberg, C. (1988). *Birds of East Africa. Supra Safari Guide No 6 Volume I*. Nairobi Kenya: Mount Kenya Sundries, 168 pages.
- [32] HBW, BirdLife, & International. (2021). *Handbook of the Birds of the World and BirdLife International digital checklist of the birds of the world*. London: HBW (Handbook of the Birds of the World) Version 6, 624 pages. http://datazone.birdlife.org/userfiles/file/species/Taxonomy/HBW-BirdLife_Checklist_v_Dec21.zip 17/09/2022.
- [33] Hockey, P. A., Dean, W. R., & Ryan, P. (2005). Cape Town: Dans J. Voelcker, *John Voelcker Bird Book Fund. 1,296 pp, 80 (un-numbered) colour plates*. Hardback: ABC Bulletin 13.2 August 2006. ISBN 0-620-34053-3: 233– 237, 4 pages.
- [34] Houde, P. (1994). Evolution of the Heliornithidae: Reciprocal illumination by morphology, biogeography and DNA hybridization (Aves: Gruiformes). *Cladistics* 10:1–19, 19 pages.
- [35] Houde, P., Sheldon, F. H., & Krettman, M. (1995). A comparison of solution and membrane-based DNA 3 DNA hybridization, as used to infer phylogeny. *Journal of Molecular Evolution* 40: 678–688, 8 pages.
- [36] Howard, G. W., Ragle, J., & Darwall, W. (2010). Integration of freshwater biodiversity in the development process throughout Africa; mobilizing information and site demonstrations: Rusizi Demonstration Site Component. *IUCN Project No. 76458-009*, 28 pages.
- [37] ICCN. (2005). Protected Areas of the Democratic Republic of Congo. . *Conservation Biology Vol 19 No 1.*, 15-22 4 pages.
- [38] ICCN. (2007). Inventaire Rapide des Zones Humides Représentatives en République Démocratique du Congo (Annuel Report 2007pdf). *The Congolese Institute for Nature Conservation (ICCN)*, 13 pages.
- [39] Jenni, D. A., & Kirwan, G. M. (2020). *African Jacana (Actophilornis africanus)*, version 1.0 . Dans J. d. Hoyo, A. Elliott, J. Sargatal, D. A. Christie, & E. d. Juana, *Birds of the World*. New York: Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY, USA, 625 pages.
- [40] Kabila, J. (2003). *Loi No 011/2002 du 29 aout 2002 portant code forestier en Republique Democratique du Congo*. Kinshasa, RDC: Journal Officiel, 25 pages. <http://www.leganet.cd/code%20Forestier/rdc-loiforestiers.pdf> 01/11/2021 .
- [41] Kitto, G. B., & Wilson, A. C. (1966). Evolution of malate dehydrogenase in birds. *Science* 153: 1408–1410, 3 pages.
- [42] Kushlan, J. A., & Hafner, H. (2000). *Heron conservation*. San Diego: Academic Press 312-330, 18 pages.
- [43] Lanyon, S. M., & Hall, J. G. (1994). Rexamination of barbet monophyly using mitochondrial-DNA sequence data. *Auk* 111:389–397, 8 pages.
- [44] Lepage, D. (2020). List of birds of the Democratic Republic of the Congo . *The Worldwide Avibase, Kinshasa*, 45 pages.
- [45] MEEATU, Convention, R., & WWF. (2014). *Atlas of Burundi's four Ramsar sites: Location and Resources*. Bujumbura, Burundi: Ministry of Water, Environment, Land Use Planning and Town Planning (MEEATU), 44 pages. <http://www.meeatu.gov.bi> 09/12/2021.
- [46] Ndayizeye, C. (2017). *Burundi Country Environmental Analysis. Understanding the Environment within the Dynamics of a Complex World: Linkages to Fragility, Conflict and Clamate Change*. Bujumbura: World Bank Group & TerrAfrica, 178 pages.
- [47] Nkezabahizi, L., & Bizimana, D. (2008). *Burundi's Important Bird Areas, Status and Trends*. Bujumbura-Burundi: Association Burundaise pour la protection des Oiseaux, 58 pages. http://datazone.birdlife.org/2008_Burundi_monitoring_report.pdf 20/06/2022.
- [48] Nkezabahizi, L., & Manirambona, A. (2011). *Burundi's Important Bird Areas Status and Trend 2010*. London: BirdLife International & RSPB (Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (UK), 36 pages.
- [49] Ntakimazi, G., Nzigidahera, B., Nicayenzi, F., & West, K. (2000). *Étude Spéciale Biodiversité (ESBio) Rapport: État de la diversité biologique dans les milieux aquatiques et terrestres du Delta de La Rusizi*. New York: LBP/PBLT/UNDP/GEF/UNOPS, 70 pages.
- [50] Ntakiyica, A. (2008). *Etat des connaissances sur les sites de distribution de la faune ornithologique au Burundi. Mémoire de Licence en sciences biologiques*. Bujumbura: Faculté des Sciences de l'Université du Burundi, 43 pages. <http://www.ub.edu.bi> 07/09.
- [51] Nunes, M. F., Filho, R. C., Roos, A. L., & Mestre, L. A. (2010). *The Cattle Egret (Bubulcus ibis) on Fernando de Noronha Archipelago: history and population trends* . Brasilia: Revista Brasileira de Ornitologia 18: 315–327, 12 pages.
- [52] Nzigidahera, B. (2006). *Études de vulnérabilité et d'adaptation aux changements climatiques au Burundi Thème: Ecosystèmes terrestres*. Bujumbura-Burundi: UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) & FEM (Fond Mondial pour l'Environnement), 66 pages.

- [53] Ockendon, N., Baker, D., Carr, J. A., White, E. V., Almond, R. E., Amano, T., et al. (2014). *Global Change Biology*. New York: Biol.20 2221-2229, 8 pages.
- [54] Olson, S. L. (1973). A Classification of the Rallidae. *The Wilson Bulletin*. Vol.85, No.4, 35.
- [55] Parejo, D., Sánchez-Guzmán, J. M., & Avilés, J. M. (2001). Breeding biology of the Cattle Egret *Bubucus ibis* in Southwest Spain. *Bird Study*, 48:367-372, 7 pages.
- [56] Ramsar, C. S. (2013). *The Ramsar Convention Manual A Guide to the Convention on Wetlands*. Iran: Ramsar Editions, Ramsar, Iran, 1971, 6th edition, 112 pages.
- [57] RDC. (2016). Loi no 15/026 du 31 décembre 2015 relative à l'eau. *Journal Officiel & , Cabinet Président, Kinshasa- DRC*, 19 pages.
- [58] RDC, C. P. (2003). Loi no 0011/2002 du 29 aout 2002 relative au Code Forestier, *Journal Officiel 43 ème année*. Kinshasa: Centre Protestant d'Édition et de Diffusion, 35 pages.
- [59] Samraoui, B., & Bélair, G. d. (1997). The Guerbes-Senhadja wetlands. Part I: an overview. *Ecologie 28*: 233-250, 17 pages.
- [60] Samraoui, F., Menai, R., & Boudjéma, S. (2007). Reproductive ecology of the Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) at Sidi Achour, north-eastern Algeria. *Ostrich*, 78(2): 481-487 Printed in South Africa, 8 pages.
- [61] Sbiki, M., Chenchouni, H., & Bachir, A. S. (2015). Population increase and nest-site selection of Cattle Egrets *Bubulcus ibis* at a new colony in drylands of north-east Algeria. *Ostrich*, 86:3, 231-237, 6 pages.
- [62] Seyler, J. R., Duncan, T., Mwanza, N., & Mpoy, A. (2010). *Democratic Republic of Congo: Biodiversity and Tropical Forestry Assessment (118/119) Final Report*. Washington, USA: USAID from the American People 209 pages.
- [63] Sheldon, F. H., Mccrackne, K. G., & Stuebing, K. D. (1995). The phylogeny of the Zigzag Heron (*Zebriulus undulatus*) and White-crested Bittern (*Tigriornis leucolophus*) estimated by DNA-DNA hybridization. *Auk* 112:672-679, 7 pages.
- [64] Sibley, C. G., & Ahlquist, J. E. (1990). *Phylogeny and classification of birds*. New Haven, Connecticut: Yale University Press, 976 pages.
- [65] Sinclair, I., & Ryan, P. (2010). *Birds of Africa South of the Sahara*. Pretoria, South Africa: Amazon, Birds-Africa-South-Sahara-Sin, 769 pages. <https://www.amazon.fr> > 08/09/2022.
- [66] Slikas, B. (1997). Phylogeny of the avian family Ciconiidae (storks) based on cytochrome b sequences and DNA-DNA hybridization distances. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 8: 275-300, 25 pages.
- [67] Stevenson, A. C., Skinner, J., & Smart, M. (1988). The El Kala National Park and environs, Algeria: An ecological evaluation. *Environmental Conservation* 15: 335-348, 13 pages.
- [68] Stevenson, T., & Fanshawe, J. (2002). *Field Guide to the Birds of East Africa: Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi*. London: T. & A.D. Poyser, 606 pages.
- [69] Steyn, P. (1980). *Black Crake feeding behaviour*. In Albatross 258: 1. Taylor PB. 1996. Family Rallidae (rails, gallinules and coots): Hoatzin to auks. Dans E. A. del Hoyo J, *Handbook of the birds of the world*. vol. 3:108-209. Barcelona: Lynx Edicions, 101 pages.
- [70] Strauch, J. G. (1978). *The phylogeny of the Charadriiformes: A new estimate using the method of character compatibility analysis*. London: Transactions of the Zoological Society of London 34:263-345, 83 pages.
- [71] Sukachev, V. N. (1964). *Osnovnye ponyatiya lesnoi biotsenologii (Basic Concepts of Forest Biocenology)*, Moscow. *Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 9 pages .
- [72] Taylor, P. B. (1996). Family Rallidae (rails, gallinules and coots). Dans J. d. Hoyo, A. Elliott, & J. S. (eds), *Handbook of the birds of the world*. Hoatzin to auks, Barcelona: Lynx Edicions. vol. 3: 108-209, 101 pages.
- [73] Tourenq, C., Barbraud, C., Sadoul, N., Sandoz, A., Lombardini, K., Kayser, Y., et al. (2001). Does foraging habitat quality affect reproductive performance in the Little Egret, *Egretta garzetta*? *Animal Biodiversity and Conservation*, 24.1: 107-116., 9 pages.
- [74] Urban, E., Fry, H. C., & Keith, S. (1986). *Birds of Africa Volume II: Gamebirds to Pigeons*. London: Academic Press 100 pages.
- [75] Wang, X., Kuang, F., Tan, K., & Zhijun, M. (2018). Population trends, threats, and conservation recommendations for waterbirds in China. *Avian Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40657-018-0106-9> 04/08/2022, 13 pages.
- [76] Weeks, P. (1999). Interactions between Red-billed Oxpeckers, *Buphagus erythrorhynchus*, and domestic cattle, *Bos taurus*, in Zimbabwe. *Animal Behaviour* 58: 1253-1259, 7 pages.
- [77] Whittingham, L. A., Sheldon, F. H., & Emlen, S. T. (2000). Molecular Phylogeny of Jacanas and its Implications for Morphologic and Biogeographic Evolution. *The Auk* 117 (1):22-32, 11 pages .
- [78] Williams, J. G., & Arlott, N. (1980). *A Field Guide to the Birds of East Africa*. <https://www.amazon.fr> > Birds-East-Africa-John-Williams 03/08/2022. London UK: Collins Grafton Street, 415 pages.
- [79] Zimmerman, D., Turner, D. A., & Pearson, D. J. (1999). *Zimmerman D. A., Turner D.A. & Pearson D.J. Birds of Kenya and Northern Tanzania*. London UK: Christopher Helm, A. & C. Black, 576 pages.